

IMPACT OF INSECURITY ON SCHOOL ADMINISTRATION, CURRICULUM IMPLEMENTATION, AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF BASIC SCIENCE STUDENTS IN NIGER STATE, NIGERIA

BY

**NKOK, Ekaette Anietie Enang (PhD)¹, ABUBAKAR Mohammed Ndanusa (PhD)²,
HUSSAINI Usman (PhD)³ & NKOK, Ubong Monday (PhD)⁴**

¹Department of Integrated Science Umaru Sanda Ahmadu College of Education, (USACOE) Minna

²Department of Mathematics Umaru Sanda Ahmadu College of Education, (USACOE) Minna

³Department of Curriculum Studies Umaru Sanda Ahmadu College of Education, (USACOE) Minna.

⁴Department of Curriculum & Teaching, Akwa Ibom State University of Education, Afaha Nsit.

Email: nkok.ekaette@coeminna.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20989832>

Abstract

This study on impact of insecurity on school administration, curriculum implementation, and academic achievement of Basic Science students in the troubled zones of Niger State, Nigeria, made use of a survey research design. The population of 10605 Basic Science students, 94 Basic Science teachers and 27 principals in all the public junior secondary schools in the region. Using simple random sampling technique, 250 students, 23 teachers and 10 principals were selected to form sample size for the study. Three questionnaires containing 10 items each on the Impact of Insecurity on school administration, curriculum Implementation, and academic achievement of Basic Science Students in Niger State, Nigeria (IISACIAABSS) was adapted from 4-point Likert scale, duly validated and the internal consistency determined to be 0.82 using Cronbach's alpha value were administered on the respondents. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation with a criterion mean of 2.50. The findings of the study revealed that, there is serious negative impact of insecurity on all facets of education. Based on the findings, four recommendations were made, among which are:- Niger State government in collaboration with local vigilante groups should provide adequate security in schools to ensure safety and reduce security financial burden on schools' administrators in the zones, and that, the federal government should come to the aids of Niger State government by providing police, military and other security operatives to combat insecurity, eradicate bandits and other terrorist groups in the state so as to eliminate teachers' fear, ensure safety and enhance concentration on their duty posts for effective service deliveries.

Keywords: Insecurity, School Administration, Curriculum Implementation, Academic Achievement, Basic Science Students.

Introduction

Insecurity has become a global issue of concern in recent time, Nigeria, one of Africa's most populous nations has not escaped the clutches of this pressing challenge. According to Aleyomi and Nwagwu (2023), various parts of the country have faced a range of security threats. With the situation worsening in the Northern part of the country, often times, armed men identified as bandits, Boko Haram, Islamic States of West African Province (ISWAP) killer herdsmen and unknown

gunmen attack the innocent inhabitants of the region, killing and maiming them (BBC,2020). From Borno, Niger, Zamfara, Katsina, Kaduna, Yobe, Adamawa, Taraba, Benue, Plateau, Nasarawa States to FCT - Abuja, nowhere is safe for Nigerians to move freely without fear of being kidnapped or robbed. Communities, roads, places of worships, schools, markets, villages and towns dwellers are attacked, injured, maimed, abducted or killed (Okpaga, et.al., 2012). It is rather pathetic that, education institutions (schools)

and the primary stakeholders (teachers and pupils/students) are the major victims of the insurgency or bandits' activities. Osaat and Ekechukwu (2021), reported that, Nigeria's education sector is under attack, particularly in the North - West and North – Central as students and teachers are no longer free to learn or teach without looking over their shoulders to see if bandits are coming. Jimoh, et. al. (2022).

This became a topical issue at the instance of the abduction of about 110 school girls from the government girls' technical and science school, Dapchi, Yobe State. (Niyi, et.al., 2023). There have been advices from concerned individuals and groups for State and Federal governments to suspend boarding school system for girls in the region until the safety of all schools can be fully guaranteed. The region as of today, is one of the most unsafe parts of the world for the education of female children. (Oyesina, 2018). Over 57 percent of schools in Bornu state are yet to reopen as they are still closed in the new school year, due to the Boko Haram insurgency in the North-East Nigeria, with a record of estimated three million children in need of emergency education support. In Niger State, the scourge of insecurity has subjected many families to distressing upsurge in violent crimes as an unfortunate reality of their daily existence (Olapeju & Peter, 2021). Indeed, quite a few local governments in Niger State such as Kontagora, Mariga, Munya, Rafi, Shiroro, and Wushishi and even the once peaceful Minna, Niger State capital, have swiftly been transformed into realms marked by bloodshed and turmoil (Usman,2024).

On 14 August 2023, This Day newspaper reported a harrowing incident in Niger State, where no fewer than 13 soldiers lost their lives to bandits, with the military also losing a helicopter during the evacuation of casualties (Okwuwada, 2023). This incident unfolded around Kundu in Rafi Local Government Area

of Niger State, leaving at least 10 other security personnel injured in the heinous attack by the bandits. Consequently, insecurity has emerged as the paramount issue afflicting Niger State in recent times, and a lasting solution remains elusive (Egonu, et. al., 2023). Unfortunately, the problem is transforming from what began as cattle rustling into kidnapping, stealing and destruction of lives and properties (Sanchi,et.al., 2022). This has caused a drastic decline on crops production, mineral resources and educational standards in the region and Niger State at large. The troubled zones are: Kontagora, Magama, Mariga, Munya, Rafi, Rijau, Shiroro, and Wushishi (Usman, 2024). The consequences of this deteriorating security situation are unquantifiable. As many families are being pushed into extreme poverty as they lose their means of livelihood, investments and even accommodations.

Most farmers could no longer access their farms and school facilities are destroyed while some educational investors move out of the state. The persistent acts of killings kidnappings and maiming of lives, has sown so much fear and anxiety in the hearts of inhabitants. Resulting to closures of schools especially boarding schools, and those tasked with overseeing the education system, like inspectors, supervisors, teachers, and even parents, grapple with profound fear in the execution of their responsibilities concerning the educational development in the state which hinders effective curriculum implementation in schools located in the region. The implications of this insecurity on education, and the overall development of the children and youth as well as on the economy and human capital development cannot be undermined. Within the pace at which bandits attack schools, government and private proprietors will be forced to shut down schools intermittently, and then for much longer. Parents and guidance on the other hand are also reluctant to send their wards to school; while

teachers and other care-givers will be reluctant to report for work.

The repercussion is the fallen standard of education inability for stake holders to implement educational curricula, and gap in the educational process (Lawal, et al., 2021) and UNICEF, (2023) reported that, the negative effects of this development on our school system can only be imagined than easily explained. The impact of insecurity on the already messed-up basic education system in Nigeria where about 13 million children are out-of-school roaming the streets, hawking, taking cattle for grazing on people's farms is dreadful (Umar, *et al.*, 2023).

Despite the attempts by the state government to find a lasting solution, the problem keeps escalating, the fundamental basics of any community is peace, dynamic economic activities, and standard education. Education needs a conducive and peaceful environment to thrive, with the main activities involving teaching and learning in a peaceful environment whereby both students and teachers feel secured. But due to unsafe schools' environment in the area, most schools have been forced to close while some have relocated to peaceful areas of the state with a high rate of drop - out of students who cannot relocate with them. In the other hands, parents and guidance whose sources of income, or means of livelihood located on the affected regions lost their sources of income and are unable to foot the bills of their children in schools which results to increase in school drop outs. Security is pivotal, especially for the effective instruction and absorption of knowledge, particularly in science subjects and mathematics.

Researchers have established relationships between teachers' effectiveness and students' academic achievement. When the teachers are affected, the students are also affected and this could inadvertently affect the teaching and

learning process which might have impact on academic achievement or the learning outcome of students. According to Nkok (2023), academic achievement is considered to be an individual's performance in class tests as well as the level of education ultimately attained. When schools operate under a very high sense of insecurity, it is unhealthy for teaching, learning and interrupts school curriculums. The rising cases of kidnapping incidents at schools in some parts of Niger State shows how vulnerable schools in these regions have become for bandits and kidnappers (Usman, 2024). It means that kidnappers, bandits, terrorists or whatever name they are called, have declared war on the education sector in the regions and by extension on the future of our students and the state at large. When teachers go to school without guaranteed of safety, it will affect their preparation and execution of the lesson. Sudden closure of schools may impact negatively on the school's curriculum implementation (Lawal, *et al.*, 2021).

Under this kind of circumstances, science students in particular may not be able to have active participation in the learning process while teachers may not be able to maximize their potentials which might result to non-implementation of curriculum. Basic Science was formally known as integrated science but due to some curriculum reforms by the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council, which allows learners appreciate the fundamental unity of science led to the change of its name (Nkok, 2023). Basic Science is integration of all science subject that deal with the study of living things and non-living things. Basic Science is taught at the primary and JSS level which provide initial theoretical and practical frameworks which are prerequisites for future study in core science subjects. The Basic Science curriculum emphasis the teaching and learning of Basic Science through the use of science laboratories

is on ensuring that teachers not only teach the processes of science but also enable sensory learners to learn scientific concepts (NERDC, 2013).

By this, the “hands” and “minds” of learners must be on scientific activities such that learners will be able to learn actively and thereby participate in knowledge construction (Nkok, 2023). But, teaching and learning of Basic Science in an in-secured environment may be counterproductive as the students are not relaxed to explore their environment for new knowledge and the teachers do not feel secured to guide the students in the explorative and hands-on learning activities in line with the curriculum’s prescription. This might have been responsible for the decline in academic achievement of students in Basic Science in the state. According to Niger State Ministry of education (2024), there has been a decline in the percentage of students who had credit pass in Basic Science from 2020 until 2024 in Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE).

The percentage of credit pass and above fell between 0.30% and 35.50% in 2023 across the government secondary schools in Niger State. Though more than 50% of the students passed at credit level in each year, there is a decline in the trend from 2022 up to 2024, the percentage of students that passed Basic Science at credit level was at 49.79%; and that of failure was at 50.21% (Niger State Ministry of Education, 2024). If this trend of failure is allowed, most students will not be qualified for science classes in senior secondary schools. Since science and technology is the bedrock of the society, the society will suffer from shortage of manpower in science related professions like medicine, engineering, agriculture, science education among others. In view of this, it’s important to investigate the impact of insecurity on schools’ administration, curriculum and academic achievement of Basic Science students in Niger State and make some recommendations that will help improve

the security situation in the state, so as to enhance peaceful environment for school activities with a view of enhancing curriculum implementation which might result to improved academic achievement of students particularly in science subjects.

Objective of the Study

- 1.To determine the impact of insecurity on schools’ administration in the troubled zone of Niger State
- 2.To determine the impact of insecurity on Basic Science curriculum implementation in the troubled zone of Niger State
3. To determine the impact of insecurity on Basic Science students’ achievement in the troubled zone of Niger State

Research Questions

- 1.To what extent does insecurity affect schools’ administration in the troubled zone of Niger State?
- 2.To what extent does insecurity affect Basic Science curriculum implementation in the troubled zone of Niger State?
3. To what extent does insecurity affect Basic Science students’ academic achievement in the troubled zone of Niger State?

Research Method

This study made use of a survey research design. The population for the study consisted of all Basic Science students, their teachers and all principals in the troubled zones of Niger State. There were 10,605 Basic Science students, 94 Basic Science teachers and 27 principals in all the public junior secondary schools in the region. Using random sampling technique, 250 students, 23 Basic Science teachers and 10 public school principals were selected for the study. Three questionnaires containing 10 items each on impact of insecurity on school administration,

curriculum implementation, and academic achievement of Basic Science students (IISACIAABSS) was constructed and administered on the respondents (students, teachers and principals) of the sampled schools. The instruments were validated by experts in test and measurements, and internal consistency of the instruments was determined to be 0.82 using Cronbach’s alpha value. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation with a criterion mean of

2.50. A calculated mean score of 2.50 and above indicates serious impact of insecurity on schools’ administration, teaching and academic achievement of students in the troubled zones of Niger State.

Results

Research Question one: To what extent does insecurity affect schools’ administration in the troubled zone of Niger State?

Table 1: Impact of Insecurity on Schools’ Administration in the Troubled Zone of Niger State

SN	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	S	Remark
1	Insecurity has affected my school’s sources of income	5	2	2	1	3.1	0.63	Agreed
2	Insecurity has affected students’ enrolment in my school	6	3	1	0	3.5	0.5	Agreed
3	Insecurity has affected job performance in my school	4	2	2	2	2.6	0.71	Agreed
4	Insecurity affects teachers’ availability and controllability in my school	6	2	2	0	3.4	0.63	Agreed
5	Insecurity affects human resources in my school	5	3	1	1	3.2	0.43	Agreed
6	Insecurity has no effect on students’ enrolment in my school	1	2	5	2	2.2	0.71	Disagreed
7	Insecurity has no effect on my school discipline strategies	1	3	4	2	2.3	0.71	Disagreed
8	Insecurity has no effect on evaluation process in my school	2	3	4	1	2.4	0.71	Disagreed
9	I do not spend greater percentage of my school income on security measures	1	1	3	5	1.8	1.4	Disagreed
10	Insecurity has no effect on quality assurance process in my school	1	2	6	1	2.3	0.71	Disagreed

SA= Strongly Agree, A= Agree. D disagree SD= strongly disagree, N- sample size and S=standard deviation

Table 1 shows the extent to which insecurity affect schools’ administration in the troubled zone of Niger State. The mean of positive items 1-5 was 3.1,3.5,2.6,3.4 and 3.2 with corresponding standard deviation of 0.72,0.65, 0.84,0.75 and aggregate mean of 3.6 which surpasses the decision-making points of 2.5 in agreement of the respondents with the items, which shows that insecurity has a great impact on schools’ administration in the troubled zone of Niger State. In the same vain, negative items 6-10 with mean values of 2.2,2.3,2.4,1.8,2.3

and corresponding standard deviation of 0.73,0.67, 0.75, 0.63, 0.75 and average mean of 3.0 in disagreement of the respondents with the negative items further affirms that insecurity is a major threat to educational administration.

Research Question Two: To what extent does insecurity affect Basic Science curriculum implementation in the troubled zone of Niger State?

Table 2: Impact of Insecurity on Basic Science curriculum implementation in the Troubled Zone of Niger State

SN	Item	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	Remark
1	My students don't take active participation in class due to fear of attack by bandits	13	5	4	1	3.30	Agreed
2	Because of insecurity, I only go to school when I have lessons	15	3	3	2	3.34	Disagreed
3	I'm always security conscious whenever I'm in my school environment	19	4	0	0	3.83	Agreed
4	I do move freely to source for instructional materials in my environment	1	1	20	3	2.10	Disagreed
5	I wish to be transferred from my present station	21	1	1	0	3.86	Agreed
6	None of my relatives has ever been victims of insecurity in the society	1	1	14	6	1.70	Disagreed
7	I can't organize extra lessons for my students because of fear of insecurity	20	1	1	1	3.70	Agreed
8	I do miss some of my lessons because of fear of insecurity	14	5	1	3	3.30	Agreed
9	I can't concentrate in class during lessons because of insecurity	15	6	2	0	3.56	Agreed
10	I hardly feel relaxed to prepare for my lessons because of insecurity	13	3	4	3	3.10	Agreed

SA-Strongly Agree A=Agree. D disagree SD= strongly disagree, N- sample size and S=standard deviation

Table: 2, shows impact of insecurity on Basic Science curriculum implementation in the troubled zones of Niger State. Items 1,2,3, 5,8,9 and 10 with mean values of 3.30, 3.34, 3.83, 3. 30, 3.56 and 3.1 and aggregate mean of 3.7 which surpasses the decision-making level of 2.5 in agreement of the respondents with the items indicates that insecurity is a major threat to teachers' job performance and

effectiveness. To this end, items 1,2,3,5,8,9 and 10 were all accepted. While items 4 and 6 with mean scores of 2.10 and 1.70 are in disagreement with the negative items.

Research Question Three: To what extent does insecurity affect Basic Science students' academic achievement in the troubled zones of Niger State?

Table 3: Impact of insecurity on academic achievement of Basic Science students in the troubled zone of Niger State.

S/n	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	S	Remark
1	I'm always afraid of going to school because of insecurity	100	60	50	40	2.8	0.8	Agreed
2	My scores in Basic Science and other subjects have gone down since bandits started attacking people in my locality	120	60	40	30	3.1	0.7	Agreed
3	I always concentrate in class without fear of insecurity.	20	30	120	80	1.9	0.75	Disagreed
4	I always do my assignment at home without fear of insecurity	30	40	100	80	2.08	0.75	Disagreed
5	My school calendar has ever been interrupted because of insecurity	10	150	50	40	2.5	0.7	Agreed
6	We can no longer do group study after school because of insecurity.	80	50	70	50	2.64	0.7	Agreed
7	My parents no longer visit my school to check my academic progress because of insecurity.	150	60	20	20	3.3	0.8	Agreed
8	My parents can no longer provide my school needs as insecurity has affected their business	140	70	20	20	3.2	0.7	Agreed
9	I can't explore my school and home environment freely for new knowledge without fear of insecurity	100	100	30	20	3.1	0.7	Agreed
10	I no longer live in school's boarding house because of insecurity	80	50	70	50	2.64	0.7	Agreed

N= sample size, SA= strongly agree, A= agree, D= disagree and SD= strongly disagree and S= standard deviation

Table 3 shows the impact of insecurity on Basic Science students' academic achievement in the troubled zone of Niger State. Items 1,2,5,6,7,8,9,10 with corresponding mean scores of 2.8,3.1, 2.5,2.64, 3.3, 3.2,3.1, 2.64 and corresponding standard deviation of 0.7,0.8,0.7,0.8, 0.7,0.7, 0.7 and average mean score of 2.91 which is greater than the decision making point of 2.5 in agreement to the items

implies that insecurity has affected Basic Science students' concentration, participation and academic achievement in the troubled zone of Niger State. Negative Items 3 and 4 with corresponding mean of 0.75 and 0.75 in disagreement with the items further shows that insecurity has no positive impact on academic achievement of Basic Science students.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from the investigation of impact of insecurity on school administration reveals that insecurity has severe negative impact on schools' administration, it affects all facets of the administration, ranging from fund raising, students' enrollment, human resources, staff availability and controllability, evaluation process, quality assurance, job performance,

school discipline and school expenditure. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Ogunode,et. al. (2021) which identified loss of manpower in educational institutions, poor quality of education, destructions of infrastructural facilities, brain-drain, closure of educational institutions, discouragement of educational pursue by children, internal displacement of learners, reduction of private

investment in education and inadequate funding of education as the effect of insecurity in the administration of educational institutions in Nigeria. Similarly, the findings of Okanezi and Ogeh (2023) which stated that, the persistence of the insecurity has led to increase in the number of out of-school children and affects academic calendar further buttress the findings of the present study.

The findings of Usman (2024) which concluded that, perceived insecurity significantly influenced and disrupts the broader learning environment, fostering an atmosphere of instability and unease, also aligns with the findings of this study. Effective school administration needs a peaceful environment. If the school environment is tensed, school managers spend a greater part of their income in securing the lives and properties of the school with no enough resources to purchase teaching and learning facilities. Most teachers work their transfer from the school, which affects the human resources while most students would either dropout of schools or relocate to safer schools causing a fall in students' enrollment, school calendars are affected because of sudden closures of schools while teaching and learning processes are always thwarted. The findings on impact of insecurity on teachers' job effectiveness reveals that, insecurity impacts negatively on curriculum implementation and teachers job effectiveness as it causes fear, lack of effective preparation, absenteeism, lack of concentration and inefficiency in the teaching process which hampers effective curriculum implementation process.

This finding is in agreement with Lawal, et al. (2021) which stated that, when a teacher goes to school and is not guaranteed of his safety, it will affect his performance. In the same vain, the findings by Osaat and Ekechukwu (2021) stated that, the insecurity in Nigeria and

especially in the Northern Nigeria is causing mass movement of professional teachers from one state to another leaving many educational institutions without teachers. Many teachers and lecturers are resigning their appointment due to insecurity in Northern Nigeria and the implication of this mass migration of teachers from this region is that, less teachers would be available to teach and this will affect the quality of education because, there will be inadequate professional teachers to attend to the students, this tandems with the findings of this study. The findings on impacts of insecurity on academic achievements of students revealed that insecurity is a major threat to academic achievement as it causes fear, leading to lack of students' interest in learning, lack of active participation during lessons, and inability to complete tasks.

This finding is supported by the findings of Usman (2024) which concluded that, insecurity negatively impacted on academic achievement, student enrollment, and the limitations in the effectiveness of implemented measures in the frontline local government areas of Niger State. The findings of Okanezi, and Ogeh, (2023) which stated that, insecurity in Nigeria is contributing to poor quality education because, school scheme of work and syllabuses are not covered in most educational institutions due to school closed down, also supports the present findings. In-fact, there is a consensus among researchers on the negative impacts of insecurity on academic achievement of students. The fall in academic achievement in Basic Science and other subjects since the onset of insecurity in the troubled zones of Niger State might have stemmed from the fact that students were afraid of bandit attacks as such could not participate actively in the learning process and could not explore their environment for additional knowledge after official lesson time, while some students were absent from school because of fear of being

attacked. Also, the trauma caused by having some relatives and sponsors in bandits' captivity or even losing them may have affected students' concentration in class activities. Basic Science is best learnt by experimentation and discovery and requires active participation of learners in the learning process, students in the areas could not take charge of their learning process because of the above mentioned factors, which might have been the major cause of the perceived drop in academic achievement of students.

Conclusion.

Insecurity has impacted negatively on all facets of educational. It's a major threat to effective service delivery of educational administrators, curriculum implementation, teachers and learners alike. The mode of learning environment is a major determinant of effective teaching and learning processes, plays a pivotal role on the curriculum implementation and learning outcome. Constant security threats in Northern Nigeria, particularly in some local government areas in Niger State has led to fear, sudden closure of schools, inconsistent academic calendars, exodus of teachers from the state, high rate of school drop -outs, low students' enrolments, lack of students' active participation in classes, teachers' absenteeism and lack of concentrations in schools activities, lack of parental supports due to crippled economic activities, destruction of school facilities, killings, kidnappings or maiming of teachers, students and other educational stake holders. These have culminated to lack of curriculum implementation in schools and poor academic achievement of learners in Basic Science and other subjects. If the educational system in the zone is to be revived, the recommendations made in this study should not be ignored.

Recommendations

1. Niger State government in collaboration with local vigilante groups should provide adequate security in schools and their environments to ensure safety and reduce security financial burden on schools' administrators in the troubled zones of the state.
2. The federal government should come to the aids of Niger State by providing police, military and other security operatives to combat insecurity, eradicate bandits and other terrorist groups in the troubled zone of the state so as to eliminate teachers' fear, ensure safety and enhance concentration on their duty posts for effective curriculum implementation.
3. The state government, parents, teachers, traditional rulers and school administrators should synergistically map out strategies to dialogue with the aggrieved youths (Bandits), sort out their grievances and bring a lasting peace to the affected areas in the state, so as to restore peaceful and smooth school activities in the troubled zones
4. Teachers, school counsellors and psychologists should utilize appropriate therapies like cognitive restructuring, systematic desensitization, cognitive modelling among other relevant therapies to disabuse students' minds from fear of insecurity, so as to enable them concentrate in their learning process for improved academic achievement in Basic Science and other subjects.

References

- Aleyomi, M. B., & Nwagwu, R. C. (2023). Strategic model for Nigeria's security and socioeconomic development. *African Identities*, 21(1), 66-86.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14725843.2020.1828041>
- BBC (2020) Nigerian states close schools after students kidnapped in Katsina .
<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-55338785>

- Egonu, N., Adibe, R., Nnamani, R., Nwaogaidu, J., & Oranye, H. U. (2023). Nigerian State and the management of armed conflicts: Rethinking the amnesty approach. *Security Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41284-023-00377-2>
- Jimoh, H. O., Gyan, D. A., & Adeniyi, N. A. (2022). Evaluating effects of insecurity of school environment on academic performance and school enrollment of secondary school students in Katsina State. *Bije-Bichi Journal of Education*, 16(1), 120-132.
- Lawal, A., Samson, B., Tukuru, A. & Aodu, A. (2021). Bandits hit 5 schools in N/west, N/central. *Blue print* (2, 491), 6.
- NERDC (2013). *The revised 9-basic education curriculum at a glance*. Lagos: NERDC Press. www.nerdcnigeria.gov.ng.
- Niyi, J. O, Conrad U. U & Victor, O. A. (2023). Insecurity challenges and higher education in Nigeria. *Best Journal of Innovation in science Research and development*. 2(4)2835- 3579
- Nkok, E.A E. (2023) *Influence of personality traits on academic achievement of students in Chanchaga local government Area of Niger State, Nigeria*. Proceedings of International Conference on Education, security and post covid sustainable development in Nigeria 1, 10-18
- Ogunode N. J. Ahaotu G N., & Obi-Ezenekwe, C U. (2021) Effects of insecurity on school administration in Nigeria. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 13(94) 2694-9970
- Okanezi, B. & Ogeh, O. W. M. (2023). Insecurity in northern Nigeria and its impact on the education of the populace . *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management (IJAEM)*. 5(3),1889-1894
- Okpaga, A., Chijioke, U. S., & Eme, O. I. (2012). Activities of Boko Haram and insecurity question in Nigeria. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 1(9), 77. <https://doi.org/10.12816/0002163>
- Okwuwada, N. (2023). The modern-day consequences, causes, and nature of kidnapping, terrorism, banditry, and violent crime in Nigeria: A comprehensive analysis. MPRA. <https://mpra.ub.unimuenchen.de/117671/>
- Olapeju, R. M., & Peter, A. O. (2021). The impact of banditry on Nigeria's security in the Fourth Republic: An evaluation of Nigeria's Northwest. *Zamfara. Journal of Politics and Development*, 2(1), 26-26.
- Osaat, S.D. ,& Ekechukwu P. C. (2021). Insecurity and educational development in Nigeria. *British International Journal of Education and Social Science*. 8(10)125-135
- Oyesina, T. (2018, February 28). NBA to FG: Suspend boarding system for girls in North-East. *New Telegraph*. 4 (1467), 5.
- Sanchi, I. D., Alhassan, Y. J., Ajibade, O. V., & Sabo, Y. A. (2022). Implications of rural banditry on educational development in Nigeria: A critical review. *Direct Research Journal of Social Science and Educational Studies*,10(5), 77-87. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-60013-0_186-1
- Umar, M. K., Ibrahim, U. K., & Adamu, I. (2023). Effects of insecurity on students' academic performance in Katsina State schools:A case study of the frontline local government areas. *Modern Journal of Social Science and Humanities*, 18, 1-9
- UNICEF (2023) More than half of all schools remain closed in Borno State, epicentre of the Boko Haram crisis in north- east Nigeria <https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/press->
- Usman, H. (2024). Overview of the perceived influence of insecurity on academic performance in front lines local government secondary schools in Niger State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Professional Development, Learners and Learning*, 6(1), 2407. <https://doi.org/10.>